

KEY INTERACTIVE TEACHING METHODS APPLIED AT THE UNIVERSITY OF MILITARY SECURITY AND DEFENCE OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article analyses the principal interactive teaching methods through the prism of their application at the University of Military Security and Defence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, with proposed formats for their implementation.

Key words: active and interactive teaching methods; discussion; round-table discussion; brainstorming; case study.

The transformations currently taking place in the system of higher education are driven by a shift towards an innovative, personality-centred and development-oriented educational paradigm, as well as by the need to utilise individuals' intellectual and creative potential for constructive activity across all spheres of life.

Unfortunately, at present, there is no clear classification of interactive teaching methods. This may be due to the absence of a distinct differentiation between active and interactive teaching methods, as the same types of methods are often classified both as active and as interactive.

The implementation of active and interactive teaching methods constitutes one of the most important directions for enhancing the training of students (cadets) at the University of Military Security and Defense of the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter referred to as the University).

In light of the above, the author examined the application of the main interactive teaching methods at the University and the specific features of their use in the educational process.

The discussion method serves as a fundamental component within the system of interactive teaching methods, being incorporated into each of them as an essential element. At the same time, discussion can also function as an independent interactive teaching method, represented by a variety of modifications that differ in the ways the discussion process is organized.

In Latin, the term "discussio" refers to investigation or analysis. In other words, it denotes a collective discussion of a specific problem or issue, or a comparison of different positions, information, ideas, opinions, and proposals.

During a discussion, participants may either complement each other or oppose one another. In the first case, qualities characteristic of a dialogue are more prominently displayed; in the second, the discussion takes on the nature of a debate, i.e., the defense of one's own position. As a rule, both of these elements are present in a discussion.

Regardless of the prevailing characteristics of a discussion—whether it takes the form of a mutually opposing debate or a mutually constructive dialogue in a professional context - the key factor in enhancing the effectiveness of any discussion is the comparison of the participants' differing positions.

Discussion Methodology

Each discussion typically unfolds in three stages of development: orientation, evaluation, and consolidation.

In the first stage, the process of “orientation” takes place, during which participants adapt to the problem itself, to one another, and to the overall atmosphere. It is in this way that a certain mindset for addressing the presented problem begins to develop.

The “evaluation” stage resembles a situation in which information and different positions are compared, and ideas are generated.

In the final stage of consolidation, the development of unified or compromise solutions, opinions, and positions is envisaged.

The “Round Table” Method

Purpose of the Method:

✧ To ensure free, unregulated discussion of the issues (topics) raised, based on placing all participants on an equal footing with one another;

✧ To facilitate systematic, problem-oriented discussion of issues in order to gain insight into different aspects of the problem.

Essential Attributes of the “Round Table”:

✧ Appropriate preparation of the room for the discussion, including the symmetrical arrangement of workspaces so that participants can see one another;

✧ Implementation of the “free microphone” principle in practice;

✧ Creation and maintenance of a pool of questions to which participants of the “round table” are expected to respond;

✧ Availability of technical means for receiving and processing incoming information, if necessary.

Variants of the Stages of Conducting a “Round Table”:

Option A

1. Brief introductory remarks by the instructor.

2. Listening to short introductory statements from the participants of the “round table.”

3. Presentation to the “round table” participants of questions submitted by the audience.

4. Development of the discussion.

5. Formulation of agreed positions on the subject under discussion.

Option B

1. Quick survey of the audience to agree on the topic and the order of proceedings.

2. Clarification of the procedure and nature of the work.

3. Responses addressing the substance of the questions posed.

4. Listening to the opinions of speakers from the audience.

5. Discovery of the truth through discursive discussion.

Option C

1. Presentation of the problem (e.g., film, photographs, etc.).

2. Introduction of the “round table” participants and listening to their judgments regarding the presented situation.

3. Implementation of the “free microphone” to gather the audience’s opinions.

4. Discussion.

5. Identification of “points of convergence” and formulation of a consensus position.

During the session conducted using this method, it is necessary to explain to the participants of the “round table” the procedure for addressing the problem questions raised during the session, as well as the deadlines for providing responses.

In conclusion, the results of the “round table” are summarized, and recommendations or feedback are provided to its participants and the audience.

The “Brainstorming” Method

“Brainstorming” (also referred to as a “brain attack”) is a type of group discussion characterized by the absence of criticism of the participants’ exploratory efforts, the collection of all possible solutions, hypotheses, and suggestions generated during the process of analyzing a particular problem, and their subsequent analysis in terms of potential for further application or practical implementation.

The “brain attack” method emerged in the 1930s as a means of collective, group problem-solving designed to stimulate creative thinking. This method can be pre-planned as a segment of a session, with its basis being the search for new principles to resolve a problem.

The stages of conducting a brainstorming session studied at the University, and recommended for use, are as follows:

1. Formulation by the instructor of the problem that needs to be solved. The problem may be real or academic in nature and serve to develop the participants’ productive thinking, flexibility, and critical thinking skills.

2. Formation of an expert group (3–4 learners) capable of selecting the best ideas and developing indicators and evaluation criteria. The instructor may participate in this stage or suggest that the participants (cadets) carry it out themselves.

3. An intellectual warm-up is conducted to bring participants into a working psychological state by activating their knowledge, exchanging opinions, and forming a common position on the problem. It allows participants to free themselves from inhibiting factors (such as fears, status-role constraints, laziness, slow reaction speed, etc.), psychological barriers, and discomfort. This activity is usually of a general nature and not directly related to the main topic or problem of the discussion. This step is carried out in the form of a rapid survey. The instructor asks participants a question to which they must provide a brief answer. If one participant hesitates, the instructor addresses another. In this way, over 10–15 minutes, participants are prepared for further active communication.

4. The actual “brain attack,” aimed at resolving the problem at hand. Idea generation begins with the instructor signaling the start of the activity. Participants formulate any solutions that come to mind, striving to avoid critical evaluation. To facilitate this, the instructor encourages the intellectual activity of the participants, prohibits any comments on the expressed ideas and suggestions, and blocks non-verbal emotional reactions from group members to what is heard. The work is conducted at the fastest possible pace. Each participant is given a few seconds to speak, which does not preclude subsequent contributions. The activity can proceed in order or randomly. The expert group records all proposed ideas using technical means and/or on paper. The overall duration of this stage is 10–20 minutes.

If productivity is insufficient, the instructor may suggest individual work, where each participant records their ideas on paper for 2–5 minutes, after which all ideas are shared simultaneously for review, comparison, and discussion.

5. Evaluation and selection of the best ideas by the expert group or by all participants of the “brainstorming” session. This stage is conducted as a group discussion, with personal attribution excluded; the focus is solely on the ideas themselves. Presentation of the ideas is managed by the instructor or members of the expert group. Evaluation follows pre-established criteria and indicators and may be qualitative or quantitative. The duration of this stage varies, and discussions should not be prematurely curtailed. If no idea meets the criteria, it may be necessary to return to the brainstorming stage for additional idea generation.

6. Summary of the results of the “brainstorming” session. The instructor summarizes the outcomes of the brainstorming session and the results of the discussion.

Analysis of Specific Situations (Case Study) - a method for activating learners' educational and cognitive activity, in which participants and instructors engage directly in the discussion of business situations or problems.

This method is characterized by the following features:

The presence of a specific situation;

Development of solutions to the situation by the group (subgroups or individually);

Public defense of the developed solutions, followed by opposing arguments;

Summarizing and evaluating the results of the session.

Criteria Distinguishing a “Case” from Other Educational Sessions:

1. The Process of Information Selection. When selecting information for a case, educational objectives are always prioritized. At the same time, the content of the situation should be highly realistic (close to real life) and capable of generating genuine interest.

2. Content. The “case” should contain measured, carefully balanced information that enables the participant to quickly grasp the problem and have all the data necessary for its resolution, while avoiding excessive or overloaded information.

3. Testing. One form of testing involves identifying the participants' reactions to the “case” in groups where it has already been applied, or in a new group, directly during the session.

4. Obsolescence. The materials of the “case” gradually become outdated, as changing situations require new approaches; therefore, they must be continuously updated.

5. Moderation of work with the case is the most common approach. In order to maximize engagement with the case, involve participants in the analysis of the situation and the decision-making process, each study group is divided into subgroups (3–5 people), which select a moderator (leader). The moderator is responsible for organizing the work of the subgroup, distributing tasks among its members, and coordinating the decisions made. It is the moderator who delivers an approximately 10-minute report on the results of the subgroup's work.

Types of Situations:

- A problem situation represents a description of a real problematic situation. The objective of the participants is to find a solution to the situation or to arrive at the conclusion that such a solution is not possible.

- An evaluation situation describes a scenario in which a solution has already been found. The objective of the participants is to conduct a critical analysis of the decisions taken and to provide a reasoned conclusion regarding the presented situation and its solution.

- An illustrative situation presents a situation and explains the reasons for its occurrence, describing the procedure for its resolution. The objective of the participants is to assess the

situation as a whole, analyze its resolution, formulate questions, and express agreement or disagreement.

- A preventive situation describes the application of previously adopted solutions, making the situation training-oriented and serving as an illustration of a particular topic. The objective of the participants is to analyze the given situation and the solutions found, using the theoretical knowledge they have acquired.

Thus, this article attempts to elucidate the main interactive teaching methods through the lens of their application at the University, along with the proposed forms of implementation. It should be noted that our higher educational institution also employs a considerable number of other teaching technologies, which will be discussed in subsequent article

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